

CALCULATION OF THE FORMULAE OF THE POLYHALIDES FROM SOLUBILITY DATA

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In this paper a new mathematical expression for the calculation of the compositions of complex compounds has been derived from solubility data, and the applicability of the method has been shown by actual calculations from the solubility of halogens in solution of halides.

Formation of a complex is usually inferred by noting the dissolution of an insoluble substance in the presence of a soluble one; but the solubility data have only in a few cases been applied for the elucidation of the composition of the complex ions formed in such solutions, as the method so far applied is not a direct one and involves lengthy and tedious calculations. The formulae of the complexes are first postulated, and then the equilibrium constants are calculated and concurrency of the constants confirms the postulated formulae (*cf.* Rosenheim and Steinhauser, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1905, 25, 103; Jakowin, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1896, 20, 38).

Halogens have often been observed to dissolve in solution of halides to form complex polyhalides according to the equation,

where H represents the halogen and R, hydrogen or an alkali metal.

Let us assume that the solubility of halogen in water = a and the solubility of halogen in a solution of halide of concentration, $c = b$.

By the law of mass action

$$\frac{[\text{Complex}]}{[RH]^n [H_2]} = K \text{ (equilibrium constant).}$$

At equilibrium point the respective concentrations of

$$[\text{Complex}] = b - a; [H_2] = a; [RH] \text{ used} = (b - a)n; [RH] \text{ unused} = c - (b - a)n$$

$$\frac{b - a}{(c - bn + an)^n a} = K$$

and for the corresponding concentrations a' , b' and c' :

$$\frac{b' - a'}{(c' - b'n + a'n)^n a'} = K$$

$$(a' = a)$$

Let $(b - a)$ be represented by s , and $(b' - a) = s'$

Hence,

$$(c - sn)^n a = K \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$(c' - s'n)^n a = K \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Dividing (1) by (2) we have,

$$\frac{s}{s'} = \left[\frac{c - sn}{c' - s'n} \right]^n$$

Taking the logarithms of both sides we have,

$$\log \frac{s}{s'} = n [\log (c - sn) - \log (c' - s'n)]$$

Expanding the right hand expression by logarithmic series we have,

$$\log \frac{s}{s'} = n \left[\left\{ \log c - \frac{s}{c}n + \frac{s^2}{c^2}n^2 - \frac{s^3}{c^3}n^3 + \dots \right\} - \left\{ \log c' - \frac{s'}{c'}n + \frac{s'^2}{c'^2}n^2 - \frac{s'^3}{c'^3}n^3 \right\} \right]$$

or

$$\log \frac{s}{s'} = n [\log c - \log c' - n(s/c - s'/c') \dots \dots \dots]$$

Since n is dependent on c , the values of $s/c - s'/c'$ and those involving higher powers may be neglected for the first approximation. Hence the equation ultimately becomes

$$\log s/s' = n \log c/c'$$

$$\therefore n = \frac{\log s/s'}{\log c/c'} = \frac{\log (b-a)/(b'-a)}{\log c/c'}$$

In the following tables, the values of n calculated by the expression derived above have been recorded for the complexes formed between (i) iodine and potassium iodide, and (ii) bromine and potassium bromide.

TABLE I.
Solubility of I₂ in KI solutions.
(Data from Jakowin, *loc. cit.*)

*KI.	*I ₂ .	n (calc.)	*KI.	*I ₂	n (calc.).
0	1.342	—	13.29	8.008	1.0199
0.830	1.814	0.9203	26.57	14.680	1.0038
1.661	2.295	0.9372	53.15	28.030	1.1526
3.322	3.052	1.9591	106.3	65.280	—
6.643	4.667	1.0299			

* Concentrations expressed in mg. mole/litre).

From Table I the value of n works out to be unity, thus showing the formation of KI₃ in the solution. It is interesting to note that the value of n has a tendency to increase with the increase in concentration of KI, thus indicating the formation of higher polyiodides with increasing quantities of KI.

TABLE II
Solubility of Br₂ in KBr solutions at 26.5°.
(Data from Worley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 1107)

*KBr.	*Br ₂ dissolved.	n (calc.)	*KBr.	*Br ₂ dissolved	n (calc.).
0	0.43	—	0.10	0.65	0.9671
0.02	0.47	1.4148	0.20	0.96	0.9658
0.04	0.51	1.0000	0.40	1.27	0.9602
0.06	0.55	1.0000	0.60	1.67	1.0352
0.08	0.59	1.4272	0.80	2.10	1.5118
			0.90	2.336	—

TABLE III
Solubility of Br₂ in KBr solution at 18.5°.
(Data from Worley, *loc. cit.*)

*KBr.	*Br ₂ dissolved.	n (calc.)	*K Br.	*Br ₂ dissolved.	n (calc.)
0	0.446	—	0.20	0.87	1.0166
0.02	0.48	1.0996	0.40	1.31	1.0669
0.04	0.52	1.2585	0.60	1.77	1.0360
0.06	0.57	0.9656	0.80	2.23	1.1565
0.08	0.61	0.9732	0.90	2.485	—
0.10	0.65	1.0518	—	—	—

* Conc. expressed in mg. mole/litre.

The values of n , as recorded in Tables II and III, show the formation of KBr₃ in all the cases, as the value works out to be unity. Here also there is a tendency of the formation of higher polybromides as shown by the increase in the value of n with higher concentrations of n . The fluctuations of the values of n at other concentrations seem to be due to the experimental errors of the investigators.

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